

DCMS AI Pilot Project Report

Snake Goods Classification through an AI Computer Vision Pipeline

Natural History Museum, London

Avellina M. Y. Leong¹, Chris Addis, Sanson T. S. Poon, Arianna Salili-James, and
Ben Scott

Institute of Zoology, Zoological Society of London

Louise Gibson and Victoria Luk

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1 Project

1.1 Aim

The objective of this project is to harness AI-driven computer vision models within a multi-model pipeline, aiming to accurately identify illegal snake goods down to the species level. Our unique approach involves training deep learning models that classify species based on the distinct skin texture patterns captured from live snake imagery, whereby the model is then generalised to recognise the same patterns in illegal snake products. This research collaborates with the Zoological Society of London (ZSL), who holds a diverse range of illegal reptile goods seized by the Border Force and Metropolitan Police. With this multi-model pipeline, we aim to assist ZSL's taxonomic identification and improve the data quality of their dry specimen collection, allowing open access of these specimens for broader scientific research and public engagement. Ultimately, this pipeline can be refined and repurposed into an application for law enforcement to distinguish between illegal and legal reptile species, thereby improving enforcement efficiency and increasing the likelihood of successful prosecution against illegal reptile trade activities.

1.2 Background

Wildlife trade is a key driver of the biodiversity crisis, contributing to the ongoing global sixth mass extinction (Ceballos et al., 2015). Although human driven events such as habitat loss, pollution and climate change are broadly researched, assessments of wildlife trade remain incomplete despite being the second most damaging human activity to global

¹avellina.leong@nhm.ac.uk

biodiversity (IPBES, 2019). Reptiles are among the most intensively traded taxa and are often exported as exotic pets, traditional medicine or as reptile leather goods (Janssen, 2021). Apart from the direct impact of reducing wild reptile populations, the reptile trade further increases the risk of disease transmission, resulting in wild population declines (Benabdallah et al., 2025). With around 90% of all traded reptile species being captured from the wild, it is undeniable that the reptile wildlife trade is directly impacting the biodiversity of wild populations (Marshall et al., 2020). To curtail wildlife trade, the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species (CITES) was created under international cooperation to regulate commercially traded species. However, with CITES mostly catering to charismatic species, they fail to safeguard thousands of reptile species, with only 9% of the traded 36% of species being monitored by CITES (Marshall et al., 2020). This has made it difficult for law enforcement and Border Force to prosecute and prevent global trade across borders. Moreover, the identification of illegally traded reptile species, which is the initial step in enforcement, continues to pose a significant challenge for border police lacking taxonomic expertise. Without proper identification, aligning species to CITES regulation appendices becomes ineffective.

The Zoological Society of London (ZSL) is a global science-led conservation organisation that works to protect endangered species, pioneer wildlife recovery programmes and combine science with public engagement for an integrated approach to global conservation. ZSL's dry biobank collections hold a diverse range of confiscated illegal reptile goods seized by the Border Force and Metropolitan Police. However, with a lack of formal identification, it is difficult to classify their own collection for digitisation purposes and to provide open access to conservation researchers and the public. Furthermore, their collaborations with the MET and Border Force have emphasised the need for taxonomic identification assistance during confiscations at the border, where there are no reptile experts at hand. Therefore, there is a need for an effective, automated method for classifying their reptile goods to the species level, which could also offer a solution to the Border Force.

Recently, a surge in AI development has shown significant potential in image-based research. In particular, improvements in a branch of AI known as computer vision has enabled interpretation of visual information, allowing object identification, pattern recognition and classification within and between images or videos (Paul et al., 2020). Over the past few years, computer vision models have found success in classifying between different snake species from snake images (Ahmed et al., 2023; Kalinathan et al., 2021; Yang and Sinnott, 2021). For example, Patel et al. (2020) utilised Fast R-CNN and ResNet models to classify 9 endemic snake species of the Galápagos Islands to achieve an accuracy of 75%. Further, Vasmatkar et al. (2020) employed VGG16, MobileNet and DenseNet models to classify 28 snake species, attaining accuracies up to 72%. However, existing research has only classified living snakes from snake images and have not branched into the classification of illegal snake goods. An outstanding challenge in classifying snake goods is the lack of a consistent shape, whereby previously snake classification models may partially rely

on the snake body shapes as one of the factors for distinguishing between species. Snake goods and skins come in various, irregular and inconsistent shapes and sizes, meaning the textual pattern of the snake skin is one of the only species defining traits, as emphasised by taxonomic experts (Tsai and Mao, 2017).

This project aims to create a proof-of-concept AI pipeline to accurately classify illegal snake goods to the species level. Through training models to classify snakes through only the textual pattern of their skin and eliminate training on snake shape or size, our pipeline can effectively be trained on the more widely available wild snake images instead of the limited reptile goods images and still converge. This will ultimately allow ZSL to identify their reptile goods in their dry collections and more broadly, assist Border Force in the future after pipeline refinement and application development.

2 Dataset and Methods

2.1 Dataset Acquisition and Initial Processing

Two datasets were utilised throughout the pipeline: 1) the live snake image dataset and 2) the snake goods image dataset. The live snake image dataset was composed of live snake images from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) database and various contributors (see acknowledgements). This culminated in a total of 2,664 images, distributed across 10 classes (10 different species) that are commonly traded in the reptile goods market (Table 1). Initial processing was applied to this dataset, filtering through images with low data quality and unclear snake patterns, producing a final, clean dataset to train the models with. The snake goods image dataset consisted of snake goods from ZSL and NHM collections, totalling 112 goods. However, only 26 goods had formal species identification (hereafter described as labelled data/images) of species our model was trained on. Unlabelled data could not be utilised to test our model as no comparisons to ground truth (true species labels) could reliably be made.

Table 1: A tabel outlining the number of images for each snake species present in the original dataset.

Species	Data
<i>Malayopython reticulatus</i>	455
<i>Python bivittatus</i>	759
<i>Python regius</i>	127
<i>Python molurus</i>	270
<i>Python sebae</i>	112
<i>Boa constrictor</i>	198
<i>Ptyas mucosus</i>	152
<i>Cerberus rhynchops</i>	58
<i>Homalopsis buccata</i>	134
<i>Ophiophagus hannah</i>	199
<i>Naja naja</i>	392
<i>Morelia viridis</i>	99

2.2 Methods Overview

In order to build a reliable model to classify snake goods, training on a large dataset of snake skins is required. However, due to the lack of available large datasets of snake goods, it is necessary to use live snake images instead for this purpose. Therefore, to generalise this to classify the snake goods dataset we implement a pipeline with 4 key stages (Figure 1) such that the classification model learns skin textural patterns rather than focusing on other factors like body shape, positioning or colour.

Figure 1: A visual representation of the AI pipeline as a flow chart. This includes segmentation (Green), data preprocessing (Light Blue), classification of snake box images (Purple) and evaluation on the snake goods images in a binary classification (Orange).

The first stage involves isolating snake skin patterns from live snake images. This segmentation process has two steps: first, generating bounding boxes to detect snakes in the images and using these to crop each image; second, segmenting the snake body from the cropped image to completely remove the background. This two-stage approach is employed because bounding boxes are easier to label manually than full segmentation masks, and the cropped images provide cleaner, more regularised input to the segmentation model. Both steps are performed using models from the Detectron2 library (Wu et al., 2019). The final output consists of masked images containing only snake skin patterns, which can then be used as our dataset so that the classifier learns snake skin patterns.

The second stage takes the segmented snake bodies and performs species classification with an EfficientnetB0 model (Tan and Le, 2019). The species included in the model are: *Malayopython reticulatus*, *Boa constrictor*, *Python molurus*, *Python bivittatus*, *Python*

sebae, *Python regius*, *Cerberus rynchops*, *Ptyas mucosus*, *Homalopsis buccata*, *Ophiophagus hannah* and *Morelia viridis*. This is then condensed into 8 classes, where the latter 5 species are grouped in a class called “Others”. This approach aimed to concentrate on key species of the snake trade and species present in the snake goods dataset. To ensure that the images we feed into the classification model only considers skin textual pattern, we firstly split the segmented snake bodies into individual boxes and additionally apply greyscaling, which eliminates the model learning snake body shape, positioning and colour as factors to classify snake species. Upon evaluation, we evaluate how well the model predicts a full snake image’s class, where the class assigned to the full image is determined by the most frequently occurring class among its classified boxes. This is hereafter known as the box classification model.

The third stage employs the box classification model by inputting labelled images of snake goods. This step assesses how well the box classification model, originally trained on live snake images, generalises to classifying snake goods. The reptile goods undergo the same processes as the live snake images, being segmented and split into boxes before being fed into the model.

The fourth stage is the final stage in testing the model’s capability in classifying snake goods. The labelled snake goods dataset is highly imbalanced. The majority of goods are made of the species *Python sebae* (14 of 26 labelled goods), while other species have only a few (1 to 6) goods each. As these species have limited numbers, it would be unreasonable to classify all present species as there is not enough snake goods data to accurately and fairly evaluate the model across all species. Therefore, a final binary classification, classifying between *Python sebae* and all other species, allows the most reasonable evaluation of the final model. The full goods images are classified from its box images and optimised through calculation of the operating threshold. This is then evaluated to understand the model’s performance in classifying full snake goods images.

2.3 Data Splitting: Train, validation and test sets

2.3.1 Segmentation Pipeline Dataset Splitting

Bounding Boxes

From the complete dataset, combining live snake images and snake skin goods totalled 1,143 images with labelled bounding boxes. This was split by 75%/10%/15% across training, validation, and test sets, respectively. These labelled images are sampled across all snake species and are annotated using VGG image annotator (VIA) (Dutta and Zisserman, 2019).

Segmentation

For the training of the segmentation model, 116 snake images with segmentation annotations were utilised, with a 75%/25% split for training and testing. These snake images were again annotated using VIA and sampled across species from the combined cropped images of the live and snake goods datasets.

2.3.2 Box Classification Model Dataset Splitting

Preparation for the box classification model involved splitting the segmented snake body data into three datasets: 70% for the training dataset, 15% for the validation dataset and 15% for the test dataset. The training and validation datasets are utilised for training and refining the model, whilst the test dataset is used as a final assessment of model performance. It is isolated from the model training process, acting as a real-world scenario of new data being fed into the model, allowing a dependable and accurate evaluation of the model’s performance on unfamiliar and unencountered data. After splitting the box image dataset, the dataset was composed of 15662 training box images, 3328 validation box images and 3361 test box images. Class distribution across snake species for the training, validation and test datasets are outlined in Table 2. The species included in the class ”Others” includes *Cerberus rynchops*, *Ptyas mucosus*, *Homalopsis buccata*, *Ophiophagus hannah* and *Morelia viridis*. Table 3 further outlines the dataset split when the box images are aggregated back into their original full images. The overall split of full images is 830 training images, 178 validation images and 179 test images. This number is reduced from the original dataset, resultant of dataset cleaning of noisy images or those that presented less than optimum segmentation.

Table 2: A table outlining dataset splitting of box images across training, validation and test datasets. These are input into the box classification model.

Class	Training dataset	Validation dataset	Test dataset
<i>Boa constrictor</i>	1890	455	420
<i>Malayopython reticulatus</i>	2314	411	517
<i>Naja naja</i>	2108	479	510
<i>Python bivittatus</i>	2198	480	531
<i>Python molurus</i>	1346	379	303
<i>Python regius</i>	986	229	109
<i>Python sebae</i>	1791	372	305
Others	3029	523	666

Table 3: Full image dataset split across training, validation and test datasets for the box classification model. This displays the full images that are represented by the box images in Table 2.

Class	Training dataset	Validation dataset	Test dataset
<i>Boa constrictor</i>	89	20	21
<i>Malayopython reticulatus</i>	106	19	22
<i>Naja naja</i>	135	27	31
<i>Python bivittatus</i>	111	29	27
<i>Python molurus</i>	66	18	13
<i>Python regius</i>	49	10	5
<i>Python sebae</i>	63	12	13
Others	211	43	47

2.4 Methods Details

2.4.1 Stage 1. Segmentation Pipeline

Data Preprocessing

A significant challenge with the model is the inclusion of non-snake elements in the segmentation masks, typically in the form of branches, leaves, or other background objects. These inaccuracies introduce noise to the classification process. In severe cases, we removed affected images from the training set for the classification model to maintain data quality.

Segmentation models

For both object detection with bounding boxes and instance segmentation, we trained models from the Detectron2 library (Wu et al., 2019). Specifically, we employed Mask R-CNN architectures (He et al., 2018) pre-trained on the COCO dataset (Lin et al., 2015), which were then fine-tuned on our training datasets (Sec 2.3.1). This transfer learning approach leverages the model’s pre-learned feature representations, which capture hierarchical visual patterns ranging from simple edges to complex object structures. By utilising pre-trained weights, we significantly reduced training time and computational costs while enhanced generalisation—particularly beneficial given the constraints of our dataset.

During fine-tuning, we applied a series of data augmentations to improve model robustness, including random horizontal flipping, brightness, contrast, and saturation adjustments, random lighting variations, and slight rotational transformations. These augmentations mitigated overfitting and improved the model’s generalisation capability, particularly for snake skin products which exhibited considerable variation in colour, texture

and morphology. We trained our object detection model for 32 epochs and our segmentation model for 64 epochs on the training datasets. Both cases utilised stochastic gradient descent (SGD) optimisation with momentum and a learning rate of 0.00025. Importantly, all annotated data was consolidated into a single class, as our models focused exclusively on detection of snake skin materials rather than classification of specific species which is the next part of our pipeline.

Evaluation

The model performance of both the bounding box and instance segmentation models were evaluated through calculations of overall average precision² across IoU³ thresholds (0.50 to 0.95) and recall metrics⁴ on our test datasets.

2.4.2 Stage 2. Box Classification Models

Data Preprocessing

Prior to model training, data preprocessing was performed on the segmented snake bodies. This involved the key step of splitting the bodies into individual boxes at a grid size of 7x7 and applying a black pixel threshold of 45%. If more than 45% of the box image contained black pixels, the box image would not be included in the dataset. These parameters allowed a balanced trade off to ensure the boxes captured enough of the snake skin pattern. For example, higher grid sizes would reduce the box image area and larger patterns may not be captured. Furthermore, other black pixel threshold values may reduce the amount of box images generated through being too strict, limiting the overall dataset size. After producing the box images, each box was resized to 240 by 240 pixels and converted to greyscale. Greyscaling was applied to eliminate colour as a classification factor, ensuring the model did not rely on it to differentiate species. This is crucial because many snake products undergo tanning or dyeing before being traded, resulting in colours that differ from those of live snakes. This assists with model generalisation to the reptile goods in later stages.

Box classification model

The box classification model is a 2D deep learning model built through the convolutional neural network architecture EfficientNetB0 (Tan and Le, 2019). Before inputting training data into the model, transfer learning with pre-trained ImageNet weights was applied, assisting in reducing training time and improving model generalisation (Russakovsky et al., 2015). Furthermore, the training data underwent image augmentation, which artificially

²Precision = True Positives / (True Positives + False Positives)

³Intersection over Union (IoU) metric measures detection accuracy as the ratio between overlapping and combined areas of predicted and ground truth bounding boxes

⁴Recall = True Positives / (True Positives + False Negatives)

expanded the dataset and reduced overfitting (Jung et al., 2020). Class weights were also applied, reducing the impact of class imbalance. After augmentation, the model performed feature extraction, which was then averaged through a 2D global pooling operation. The pooled features were subsequently passed through a fully-connected layer with a random dropout rate of 0.2. The model's output layer employed a softmax activation function that created classification probabilities for all 8 classes. Overall, the model trained for 50 epochs.

Evaluation

Evaluation occurred in two portions. Firstly, the model performance of classifying box images themselves was evaluated on the test dataset. Precision, recall and F1 scores⁵ were calculated for each of the 8 classes. Furthermore, the overall accuracy⁶, AUC-ROC (Area under curve of the receiver operating characteristic) score, ROC (receiver operating characteristic) curve plot⁷ and confusion matrix⁸ were produced.

Secondly, we evaluated how well the class predictions of the box images could classify the full image they originated from. To achieve this, we first applied majority thresholding, where the class assigned to the full image is determined by the most frequently occurring class among the classified box images. We then calculate precision, recall, F1 scores, overall accuracy and produce a confusion matrix to evaluate how well the model classifies whole snake images from the test set.

2.4.3 Stage 3. Application to Snake Goods

Data Preprocessing

Snake goods images underwent the same preprocessing as the live snake images. They are segmented to eliminate background noise, then split into boxes, resized to 240 by 240 pixels and finally converted to greyscale. This ensures the goods are in the same format as the snake images before being input into the model. Notably, the snake goods were treated as a test set and were not exposed to the box classification model during training, ensuring it simulates unfamiliar and unencountered data. This ensures that the evaluation results reflect how the model will perform on future inputs of snake goods data.

Application to snake goods

The snake goods box images were input into the box classification model as a test set to assess classification of the snake goods box images. Critically, not all classes the model was trained on were present in the snake goods dataset. Only 6 of the 8 classes were

⁵F1 score = $2((\text{Precision} * \text{Recall}) / (\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}))$

⁶Accuracy = $(\text{True positives} + \text{True Negatives}) / \text{Total Samples}$

⁷ROC curve = a plot of True Positive Rate against False Positive Rate

⁸Confusion matrix = a matrix displaying true positives, true negatives, false positives and false negatives

present, namely *Malayopython reticulatus*, *Boa constrictor*, *Python molurus*, *Python sebae* and *Python regius*.

2.4.4 Stage 4. Binary Classification of Snake Goods

Binary Classification

The last stage of the pipeline is to test the model's capability in classifying snake goods using the classifications of the goods box images. Notably, the labelled snake goods dataset is highly imbalanced, where the goods are highly skewed towards *Python sebae* (14 of 26 labelled goods). The rest of the goods dataset is composed of *Boa constrictor* (2), *Malayopython reticulatus* (1), *Python regius* (2), *Naja naja* (6) and *Python molurus* (1). As these species have limited numbers, it would be unreasonable to classify all species as there is insufficient data to accurately and fairly evaluate the model across all species. Therefore, a binary classification, classifying between *Python sebae* and other snake species, allows the most reasonable evaluation of the final model.

Evaluation of full reptile goods image

Evaluation of the full snake goods images classifying between *Python sebae* and Other snake species occurred in two portions, similar to the box classification model.

Firstly, the model performance in classifying *Python sebae* box images and other goods box images were evaluated. Precision, recall and F1 scores were calculated for the 2 classes. Then the overall accuracy, AUC-ROC score, ROC curve plot and confusion matrix were produced.

Secondly, we evaluated how well the goods box images could be used to classify the full goods images when classifying between *Python sebae* and Other snake species. This involved calculation of the operating threshold, which is the probability threshold at which a full goods image is classified as *Python sebae*. By finding the operating threshold, we maximise classification accuracy at the full goods image level, balancing false positives and false negatives effectively. The operating threshold was calculated through systematically testing different classification thresholds across full image level predictions. An operating threshold of 0.72 was then applied to the goods box images, grouping classified box images to their full goods image and using the threshold to determine the overall and final class of the full goods image. Evaluation involved calculating precision, recall, F1 score, overall accuracy and producing a confusion matrix.

3 Model Performances

3.1 Bounding Box Model

The bounding box model, evaluated on our test dataset, demonstrated strong performance with an overall average precision of 0.650 across IoU thresholds from 0.50 to 0.95. The model achieved excellent precision in detecting the majority of the body of the snake (0.897 at IoU=0.50) and maintained robust performance at stricter thresholds (0.721 at IoU=0.75), though small parts of snakes were occasionally missed. The consistent recall metrics (0.70) indicated effective detection capabilities as the majority of snakes are detected. Notably, performance degradation was primarily observed in challenging scenarios involving lower quality, blurry, images, or partially screened snakes—conditions that were suboptimal for our subsequent classification tasks. Despite these challenges with difficult images, the model provided reliable cropped images which contained the majority of available skin texture data.

3.2 Segmentation Model

Snake segmentation evaluated on our test dataset of cropped images again showed strong performance with an overall Average Precision (AP) of 0.752 across IoU thresholds from 0.50 to 0.95. The model again performed excellently in detecting large parts of the snake bodies (1.000 at IoU=0.50) but lost some precision at higher thresholds (0.845 at IoU=0.75).

3.3 Box Classification Model Results

The box classification model produced two evaluation results: 1) assessing model performance on individual snake box images, and 2) using the classifications of individual box images to determine the classification of full snake images.

Evaluation on the snake box images exhibited high AUC-ROC scores ranging from 0.86 to 0.95 across 8 classes. The precision, recall and F1 scores are summarised in Table 4, with an overall accuracy of 0.67. To further analyse model performance, the confusion matrix and ROC curve were examined (Figures 2 and 3). The confusion matrix highlights prediction results, while the ROC curve illustrates model performance at varying threshold values by plotting the true positive rate against the false positive rate.

Table 4: Classification Metrics of the box classification model on snake box images. The 8 classes and corresponding precision, recall and F1-scores are displayed.

Species	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
<i>Boa constrictor</i>	0.81	0.70	0.75
<i>Malayopython reticulatus</i>	0.65	0.72	0.68
<i>Naja naja</i>	0.69	0.79	0.73
<i>Python bivittatus</i>	0.66	0.78	0.72
<i>Python molurus</i>	0.61	0.37	0.46
<i>Python regius</i>	0.51	0.60	0.55
<i>Python sebae</i>	0.66	0.59	0.62
Others	0.64	0.60	0.62

Figure 2: A confusion matrix demonstrating true positives, true negatives, false positives and false negatives across snake classes on the box images.

Figure 3: An ROC curve plotting the true positive rate against the false positive rate, demonstrating classification across different thresholds. The dotted blue line represents a trivial model at 0.5 AUC.

The second evaluation, representing the true performance of this model, employed a majority thresholding approach, grouping individual box image classifications to determine the overall classification of full snake images. This method resulted in a higher overall accuracy of 0.77. The precision, recall and F1 scores for this evaluation are presented in Table 5. The high performance metrics suggest that leveraging individual box images for full-image classification enhances overall model reliability. The confusion matrix (Figure 4) further illustrates correct and incorrect classifications per full image.

Table 5: Classification Metrics for full snake images after applying majority thresholding on the classified box images.

Species	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
<i>Boa constrictor</i>	0.86	0.86	0.86
<i>Malayopython reticulatus</i>	0.74	0.91	0.82
<i>Naja naja</i>	0.72	0.90	0.80
<i>Python bivittatus</i>	0.70	0.96	0.81
<i>Python molurus</i>	0.56	0.38	0.45
<i>Python regius</i>	0.75	0.60	0.67
<i>Python sebae</i>	0.89	0.62	0.73
<i>Others</i>	0.88	0.62	0.73

Figure 4: A confusion matrix demonstrating true positives, true negatives, false positives and false negatives across snake classes for the full snake images in the test set following majority thresholding.

3.4 Binary Classification of Snake Goods Results

Binary classification of snake goods of *Python sebae* vs Other snake species produced two evaluation results: 1) assessing model performance on individual goods box images, and 2) using the classification of box images to determine the classification of full goods images, allowing a final classification of the individual snake goods item.

For the classification of *Python sebae* vs Other species, the model achieved a high precision of 0.71, a recall of 0.90 and an F1 score of 0.79, indicating that the model was highly effective in correctly identifying this species. The classification of other snake species also presented high precision (0.79), but a lower recall (0.52) and F1 score (0.63). The overall accuracy attained was 0.73. A breakdown of the model’s predictions is visualised in the confusion matrix (Figure 5), which illustrates the distribution of correct and incorrect classifications across both classes. The ROC curve (Figure 6) displays the classification of *Python sebae* across different thresholds.

Figure 5: A confusion matrix demonstrating true positives, true negatives, false positives and false negatives between *Python sebae* and the Others class.

Figure 6: An ROC curve plotting the true positive rate against the false positive rate, demonstrating classification of *Python sebae* across different thresholds. The dotted blue line represents a trivial model at 0.5 AUC.

The second evaluation aimed to assess the model’s ability to classify full goods images by grouping the classifications of individual box images and applying an operating threshold. This determined the final classification of the snake goods item. This approach resulted in an improved overall accuracy of 0.77. *Python sebae* presented a high precision (0.79), recall (0.79) and F1 score (0.79), demonstrating a balanced and consistent performance. Similarly, the classification of other snake species also displayed a high precision (0.75), recall (0.75) and F1 score (0.75), illustrating the improvement of applying the operating threshold to classify goods images. The confusion matrix (Figure 7) illustrates a

lower number of false positives and false negatives, further demonstrating the effectiveness of applying an operating threshold to improve the classification accuracy of full goods images.

Figure 7: A confusion matrix demonstrating true positives, true negatives, false positives and false negatives between Python sebae and the Others class of full snake good items.

4 Discussion and next project phase

The AI pipeline demonstrates an effective and innovative approach to classify illegal snake goods based on distinctive textual skin patterns of snakes. A key contribution of this work is addressing the challenge of training a model on images of live snakes while ensuring its ability to generalise to snake products, given the scarcity of goods data to train the model with. Each component of the pipeline exhibits strong evaluation metrics across multiple classes, highlighting its robustness and reliability. With additional data, time, and resources, this pipeline has the potential to develop into a digitisation or assistive tool for the ZSL and the UK Border Force.

4.1 Snake Segmentation Pipeline

The segmentation pipeline with the two-stage bounding box and segmentation model is effective for our purposes of providing a dataset of segmented snake skins. The model demonstrated a strong performance in the final segmentation, presenting an overall average precision of 0.752 across IoU thresholds from 0.50 to 0.95. Although the model illustrated excellence in detecting snake bodies (1.000 at IoU=0.50), precision was partially lost at higher thresholds (0.845 at IoU=0.75). This could be attributed to the difficulty in detecting the entire body of the snake, particularly when trying to detect

snakes that span the image with heads and tails that appear out of focus. The model performed better, for example, when segmenting compact, coiled snakes. Partially obstructed snakes further pose challenges, e.g. snakes partly covered by branches and leaves, as the model can falsely include these in the segmentation or neglect other sections of the snakes. Again, most snakes were successfully segmented with average recall across IoU thresholds at 0.785.

Through estimates we can calculate the percentage of snake skins returned, $0.7 \times 0.785 = 0.55$ (bounding box recall \times segmentation recall) such that we return just over half of all snake skin inputs into useable data for our classification model. While this can be improved by increasing the amount of training data by annotating more snakes, particularly for challenging images, it is worth noting a large fraction of snake skin that is neglected by the pipeline is from lower quality snakes images. Improving the segmentation pipeline therefore, while beneficial, will not provide orders of magnitudes improvement in available data for the classification training. As mentioned in Section 2.3.1, the segmentation pipeline should be robust to not just adding more snake data but also different snake species.

4.2 Box Classification Model

The strong box classification model performance indicates that the model effectively classifies snake species based on box images. The most significant factor is the strong performance when aggregating these classifications to classify the species of full snake images, demonstrating the efficacy of using classified box images for the classification of full images. The model achieved an overall accuracy of 77%, indicating high effectiveness in correctly classifying true instances among all predicted instances. The confusion matrix further highlights the low number of false positives and false negatives, with species such as *Python sebae* only having one misclassification. This demonstrates that the model can differentiate between species through skin textual pattern alone effectively.

In regards to individual species performance, the model performed well on most species and exceptionally well for *Boa constrictor*, *Malayopython reticulatus* and *Naja naja* classes, with F1-scores of 0.86, 0.82 and 0.80 respectively. These high F1-scores illustrate the model's strong ability in distinguishing these species, effectively balancing precision and recall. However, the model performance for one class, *Python molurus*, was comparatively weaker. It presented the lowest F1-score of 0.45, indicating significant challenges in correctly differentiating this species from the others. Further, as both the precision (0.56) and recall (0.38) were low, the model often misclassified *Python molurus* and failed to identify many true instances. However notably, *Python molurus* only has 13 full images in the test set. If the dataset is increased in future, a more balanced and fair evaluation of the model's ability to identify *Python molurus* can be obtained.

4.3 Binary classification of snake goods

The results of the binary classification illustrates that the box classification model generalises to snake goods, demonstrating that snake skin textual pattern alone can be used to differentiate snake species. Overall, the model achieved an accuracy of 77%, indicating that it correctly classified 77% of the goods images. Examining the individual class performances, the model performed comparably for the Others and *Python sebae* classes, presenting a precision of 75% and 79% respectively. These results indicate that the model is effective in distinguishing between these two classes, although some misclassifications still occurred. The confusion matrix provides further insights into these misclassifications. 3 of the 12 instances of the Others class were misidentified, whilst 3 of the 14 *Python sebae* class were misidentified. These errors suggest that while the model distinguishes the two classes reasonably well, there remains a small degree of overlap. This is likely due to *Python sebae* skin patterns being highly similar to other python species present in the Others class. However, with a high overall accuracy, the model can effectively identify *Python sebae* which is present on the CITES II appendix and EU Wildlife Trade Regulations Annex B (CITES, 2025). This demonstrates that our proof-of-concept pipeline can classify highly trafficked snakes that are highly regulated internationally.

4.4 Future Steps and Project Implications

This proof-of-concept has the potential to be scaled up to functional application in the future, supporting the efforts of ZSL and the Border Force. To achieve this, it would be essential to expand the training dataset, specifically in terms of both the diversity of endangered or highly traded species listed under CITES and the number of images per species. In particular, increasing the data for underrepresented classes such as *Python molurus* and *Python regius* would enhance the model's ability to identify these species by reducing class imbalance. Increased collaboration with other institutes could facilitate the acquisition of high-quality data. Additionally, access to a larger number of labelled snake goods is critical, as this was the largest limiting factor in testing the model's classification performance on snake goods. Addressing this would require herpetology experts and curators to identify more snake goods at the species level within the existing dataset, alongside the acquisition of additional external goods data. Furthermore, there is potential for continuing this research in collaboration with ZSL, possibly through the ECOSolve grant for AI innovation, which funds projects focusing on utilising AI methods to respond to environmental crime. With additional time and resources, improvements to the proof-of-concept pipeline are highly foreseeable. In terms of digitisation, the project has enabled all of ZSL's reptile goods collection to be digitised and will be released on a public facing website that will be launched in the near future.

Once the pipeline has been refined to classify a broader range of snake species and can be fairly evaluated on the equivalent range of snake goods, deployment as an app can begin.

This phase may include collaboration with a full stack software engineer experienced in languages such as React Native and Python to develop the mobile application (Brito et al., 2018). The app would allow users to take a photo of snake goods with their phones, process the image through the classification pipeline and generate an output that describes the species classification, its CITES status, Red List Index ranking and model's confidence percentage. This would allow users to make an informed decision about what species the snake goods item belongs to. This would be especially vital to Border Force efforts in tracking wildlife trade. As Border Force staff do not have taxonomic or herpetological knowledge, this AI-driven app would deliver a cost-efficient method to control UK borders as staff would not require additional training. The app may also assist with conservation work in the field or confirming snake skin collections in museums and institutions, acting as a well rounded assistive tool for snake species identification.

Furthermore, discussions with intelligence and research officers Gago Palacios and Andrew Mchugh of the Met Police Wildlife Crime Unit further highlighted another potential collaborative project regarding the wildlife trafficking of songbirds. The trafficking of birds is one of the most profitable trades, where a single rare parrot can sell up to \$1000 USD. These birds are caught in immense numbers, with studies estimating that 65,000 to 78,500 parrots are captured annually in Mexico, contributing to the rapid decrease of wild populations (BirdLife International, 2021). To combat this high-impact trade, AI technology can play a pivotal role by leveraging bioacoustic detection and classification. By training models to recognise and differentiate bird calls, authorities can rapidly identify species during border seizures, enhancing enforcement and protection efforts.

5 Conclusion

This project has introduced a unique methodology and AI pipeline that can solely utilise the skin textual patterns of snakes skin to classify the species of snake goods. By leveraging computer vision models for segmentation and classification, alongside a box-splitting method to ensure that only pattern information is utilised for species identification, the project demonstrates that a pipeline trained on images of live snakes can generalise effectively to the classification of snake goods. This approach presents significant potential for scaling, as the pipeline can be trained on the more readily available images of live snakes, with confidence that the model will generalise to snake goods classification. With further development and resources, this project can be developed into a working app, assisting ZSL in identifying their biobank dry collections and further supporting Border Force in distinguishing illegal species, increasing the efficacy of prosecution against individuals who contribute to wildlife trafficking and the illegal trade of reptiles. Ultimately, this could contribute to combating global biodiversity loss among key reptile species and help mitigate biological risks, such as the transmission of diseases. By enabling the rapid and accurate identification of snake goods, this solution could make the initial step in addressing illegal

wildlife trade more accessible and effective than current methods.

Supplementary Materials

The code for this project is available to view on [GitHub](#).

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